

Site: SPHINX Season NS 80

Area: EST Square N1/E9-10 Locus Number (2) 25/VI/80

Progress of Excavation All of (1b) taken up by 10:30 (2) Shows loose
clean sand across square - probably not pure as seem to be traces
of sand w/ mod. debris in spots 12:30: Locus now assuredly
loose clean sand. Much more sherd material coming up. At first
glance a mixture but some ribbed neck fragments [EST XI - clearing
along gabel ledge to N (clearing E-wards) they come down to
packed limestone, sand rubble getting 1 large granite frag, what looks
like O.K. sherds - CRW conical bottom, ND burnished RW. with
Tsmain, had them stop here to expand clearing of mod sand, garbage]

Locus Description Clean Sand Loose (OVER)

Location in Square Across Square

Under Locus (1b) Over Locus _____

Locus Dimensions _____

Levels SW: 8.83; SE: 9.48; NE: 9.74; NW: 8.98 CENTER: 9.25

Analysis of non-artifactual materials _____

Handwritten calculations:
$$\begin{array}{r} 10.125 \\ - 9.79 \\ \hline 0.335 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 8.83 \\ - 7.62 \\ \hline 1.21 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 9.48 \\ - 8.98 \\ \hline 0.50 \end{array}$$

Handwritten calculation:
$$\begin{array}{r} 7.62 \\ + 2.63 \\ \hline 10.25 \end{array}$$

Handwritten calculations:
$$\begin{array}{r} 10.125 \\ - 1.42 \\ \hline 8.705 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 10.125 \\ - 9.48 \\ \hline 0.645 \end{array}$$

30/vi/80 Yesterday (Sunday 29/vi/80 and SAT 28/vi/80)
clearing continued in ② CLEAN SAND from E-W in S half
of Square. 29/vi/80 some chunks of asphalt and cement came up
in darker brown sand, w/ more apparently Roman pottery. I think
they were moving into a lens of mod. accumulation, whereas the
clean sand is more or less ancient. Today back half of small
terracotta sphinx came up. w/ continued Roman looking pottery.

